

SEEING IS KNOWING

Society of Advanced Inter-Departmental Discussion

presents

PANOPTICON SURVEILLANCE |

NEWSLETTER
APRIL 2026

State, surveillance,
and the role of
technology_

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THE PANOPTICON

WRITTEN BY : ZAINAB NAZKI

The Panopticon was an idea conceived by Jeremy Bentham in the 1800's. It was an architectural design for prisons that allowed the inmates to be monitored at all times. A tall tower at the center of a circular prison overlooks all the prison cells and the prisoners. The tower emits bright lights towards the cells, allowing the prisoners to see the outline of the tower but not whether someone is actually propped up there, watching them.

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The prisoners are visible, but to them, their surveillant is invisible.

"The Panopticon mechanism arranges spatial unities that make it possible to see constantly and to recognize immediately," Foucault states.

Foucault picked up on this concept in his book "Discipline and Punish" (1975). He gives the example of a seventeenth-century plague-ridden town, where the residents are very closely monitored.

● PARALLELS

They aren't allowed to leave, even in the case of someone's death, and their every move is registered. He discusses the exercise of power and surveillance over a confused society such as this. The plague gives rise to this disciplinary project that allows the leper to be excluded from society. Parallels are evident between the lepers at that time and the lower rung of society today, like the marginalized. Surveillance becomes so embedded in their psyche that they believe they are being surveilled even when they aren't, since they have no way to prove otherwise. Foucault says that "Visibility is a trap. One is seen, but they cannot see, he is the object of information and never the subject in communication." This instills a state of self-surveillance in the people, who begin to do the job for their surveillant without actually having access to any of the power. Foucault uses the model of the panopticon as a metaphor to explain how power and surveillance function in post-industrial society.

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Since the release of this book, we have witnessed a dramatic escalation in surveillance, and the concentration of power has never been so unrestrained. To be more specific, unlike Bentham's model with one tower, everyone today more or less carries a portable surveillance tower of their own, in their pockets and hands. Panopticism doesn't need to feel like tyranny; we take pleasure in our discipline, and today, more than ever, we smile at the tower while taking funny selfies.

In 2013, Edward Snowden came out as the whistleblower who leaked classified documents related to the USA's mass surveillance programs. He maintains that our phones are windows into even the most intimate parts of our lives for the government; every activity on our phones is evidence of our presence. He uncovered surveillance programmes like PRISM and Tempora. He claims that any device with a camera and speaker can be hacked. We see people covering up their laptop cameras, feeble attempts at protecting their privacy. All this while their phone collects data on their sleep schedule, the number of steps they take, their sexuality, and much more.

For the first time in history, surveillance has infiltrated the public's brains and collected data regarding our thought processes. Algorithms closely monitor what we pay attention to; they curate content based on our behavioural data, selling us services in exchange for our data. This sort of curation tends to create echo chambers for most of us.

The digital panopticon has created an asymmetry in knowledge and power while limiting our choices for privacy. These algorithms are capable of recording norms and values at an individual level, and then, through that, possess the power to normalize anything. Power enables one to shape knowledge as it is known.

The perfect algorithms subdue us even further, like the lotus eaters in the Odyssey. Bright screens illuminate to stop us in our tracks and overwhelm us. We are fed lotuses that make us forget time, our purpose, and any worthwhile ideas we might possess. Affecting our critical thinking and reasoning, which allows the powerful to maintain their position, and for us to accept ours. Edward Snowden talks about, *"Our exposure to an indigestible mass of shortest form opinions that are purposefully selected by algorithms to agitate us on platforms that are designed to record and memorialize our most agitated reflexive responses."*

In a modern context, this means that big-tech CEOs have the power to influence the norms and values of our time. This impacts people's moral development. They get to own all of our data, while we essentially know nothing about them. We submit ourselves and our lives to them, our thought process infiltrated by the way algorithms work. All this data travels through the data pipelines into huge data centers. There is data of every single move we make, even if it's useless, in hopes that it might prove otherwise sometime. Everything we do now lasts forever.

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In response, Edward Snowden, then-Director of the National Security Agency of the USA, pointed towards, as he mentions it, “The arrogance of an individual who looked upon the activity of the NSA and believed his ethical judgment trumped the judgment of his co-workers, his leadership, the President.” The idea of resistance towards surveillance is seen as so baffling by the people in power that they almost confuse it with arrogance. Our data is used to infiltrate our knowledge systems, to shape the way we think and believe. The panopticon has become stronger, taller, and more omnipresent than before.

In today's age, the panopticon is embodied by the widespread modern technology that stores our data. Our smartphones record every move we make in and out of them, showing us what we think of even before we verbalize it. At times, it bombards us with content about something we might have mentioned in a passing conversation just around our phones. In moments like these, a feeling settles in our stomach, and that feeling is distinctly of someone or something watching us. A light from a high tower shines on us, making us hyper visible to the audience of a few elite and powerful.

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RESOURCES

Latest opportunities for research, internships and other educational positions (Logistics vertical)

Internship/ Program	Organisation	Who can apply	Timeline	Link
NITI Aayog Internship	Niti Aayog	UG/PG/Research students	Rolling (monthly)	https://workforindia.niti.gov.in/intern/
Public Policy Intern	The Reppro	Students or recent graduates in Public Policy, Law, Economics, Political Science, or related fields with strong communication and analytical skills.	Full time internship	abhishrut@thereppro.com
Job in Research, etc	Brower Group Asia	Interested applicants	Experienced UG degree holder	https://lnkd.in/gdHtWshY
Prime Minister's Internship Scheme (PMIS)	Ministry of Corporate Affairs	UG / PG / Young Graduates	Jan – Feb 2026	https://pminternship.mca.gov.in/
Ministry of External Affairs (MEA) Internship	MEA	UG / PG students	Feb – Mar 2026	https://internship.mea.gov.in/
RBI Summer Internship	Reserve Bank of India	PG / Professional students	Dec 2025 – Jan 2026	https://opportunities.rbi.org.in/
RBI Research Internship	Reserve Bank of India	PhD / Research Scholars	Mar – Apr 2026	https://opportunities.rbi.org.in/
SEBI Internship Programme	SEBI	UG / PG / Professional courses	Jan – Feb 2026	SEBI Young Professional Program / Internship

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Internship/ Program	Organisation	Who can apply	Timeline	Link
TRAI Internship	TRAI	UG / PG students	Jan – Mar 2026	http://traigov.in/careers/tra-internships
UIDAI Internship	UIDAI (Aadhaar)	UG / PG / Tech students	Feb – Mar 2026	https://uidai.gov.in/en/about-uidai/work-with-uidai/internship-in-uidai.html
MyGov Internship	MyGov India	UG / PG / Content & Policy students	Rolling	https://www.mygov.in/
MoSPI Internship (Official Statistics)	MoSPI	UG / PG students	Jan – Feb 2026	https:// internship.mospi.gov.in /
Digital India Internship	NIC / MeitY	UG / PG / Tech students	Dec 2025 – Jan 2026	https://dii.nic.in/
ISRO Internship / Student Project Trainee	ISRO / Dept of Space	Engineering / Science students	Jan – Mar 2026	https://www.isro.gov.in/ InternshipAndProjects. html
ICMR Internship	Indian Council of Medical Research	Life Science / Public Health students	Jan – Mar 2026	https:// www.icmr.gov.in/
LOTUS Programme	Japan Science and Technology Agency	PG / Professional students	13 Mar- 9 June	jst-india@jst.go.jp

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Internship/ Program	Organisation	Who can apply	Timeline	Link
Enterprising intern	Catalab	Interested applicants	Available	careers.catalab.in
Research Intern	CEEW	Interested applicants	Rolling	recruitment@ceew.in
Research Associate	CENSE	Interested applicants	Full time internship	comms@censeindia.org
Research	AIWC	Final year UG/PG students	Available	sanya.aiwc@gmail.com
Fellowship	SATYARTHI	Interested applicants	Available	fellowship@satyarthimovement.org
Carnegie India Internships	CARNEGIE	UG degree holder in AI, law, economics	One year	https://carnegieendowment.applicantpro.com/jobs/4019943
Gender Policy Intern	WISE	Interested applicants	Available	https://lnkd.in/gdbdkckFT
Communication Intern	Uchicago Center	UG degree holder	Available	https://lnkd.in/gYRDdSe

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Internship/ Program	Organisation	Who can apply	Timeline	Link
Economic Analysis and Public Finance Internship	NFPRC	UG/PG students	Feb - March	internship@nationfirstpolicy.org
Research Internship	The ISPU	UG/PG students	Available	bit.ly/ ISPUResearchIntern
Ecoversities Writing Fellowship	Ecoversities	Reseearcher/writer/ storyteller	Available	linktr.ee/ecoversities
Narrative writing Fellowship	Zubaan and the Parang	Interested applicants	Available	www.zubaanprojects.org
Content and Social Media Intern	Silly Goose Press	Interested applicants	Available	sillygoosepress.com/ internships
The Indigenous Climate Knowledge Fellowship	Himalayan Climate Watch Network	Storytellers	Available	https://hcwn.org/ fellowship

ENTRIES

CULTURAL CAPITALISM, PANOPTICON AND THE OBJECTIFICATION OF THE SUBJECT

WRITTEN BY : ARUSHI VERMA

“Google is to surveillance capitalism what the Ford Motor Company and General Motors were to mass-production-based managerial capitalism.”

-Shoshana Zuboff, *The Age of Surveillance Capitalism*

Shoshana Zuboff in her book ‘*The Age of Surveillance*’ described Surveillance capitalism as a new economic order and a parasitic logic that claims human experience as free raw material for translation into behavioural data.

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This kind of behaviour shifts from predictions to modifications leading competitive surveillance capitalists to move beyond simply knowing behaviour to shaping it. Micheal Foucault developed the concept of Governmentality which represented a shift in the exercise of power from traditional sovereignty to governance where the population itself becomes the object of rule.

● FOUCAULT AND POWER

For Foucault BioPower, Governmentality and Subject can only be studied collectively. A subject is a product of specific power or knowledge regimes. A man’s subjectivity is inseparable from subjugation. A man becomes a subject to someone else through control and dependence or when it is tied to one’s own identity through conscience. There is a content process of subjectification and simultaneously a process of being turned into an object of society and self (objectification).

Alexandre Kojève in his book ‘*Introduction to the Reading of Hegel Lectures On the Phenomenology of Spirit*’, wrote that “ *If man is nothing but his becoming, if his human existence in space is his existence in time or as time, if the revealed human reality is nothing but universal history, that history must be the history of the inter- action between Master and Slavery: the historical "dialectic" is the "dialectic" of Master and Slave.*”

The existing Surveillance Capitalism is generating Slaves/ Docile bodies for the economy. The Slave do not have the power of their own. It completely relies on the master for its survival.

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Micheal Foucault, Panopticon covers the similar perspective. The Panopticon is a structure composed of an annular (ring-shaped) building at the periphery and a tower at the center. The peripheric building is divided into individual cells, each extending the full width of the ring. Every cell has two windows, one on the inside facing the central tower, and another on the outside allowing light to pass through the cell from one end to the other. By placing a supervisor in the central tower and the subjects in the cells, the effect of backlighting is achieved. This makes the "small captive shadows" in the peripheral cells stand out precisely against the light, making them perfectly individualized and constantly visible to the guardian in the tower. The tower makes the inmates in the cell visible and unverifiable. The guard can easily look at the inmates but they will not have the knowledge of whether they are being watched.

The inmates become "The Subject of their own Objectification". The Panopticon is to induce in the inmates a state of conscious and permanent visibility that assures the automatic functioning of power. This is a great power in a silent, impersonal, and almost automatic manner.

This is a disciplinary mechanism. The classical age discovered the body as object and target of power. A docile body may be subjected to be used, transformed and improved. Institutions like Prison, Hospitals, Schools and the military are a way of disciplining. Discipline increases the economic forces/ utility of the body and diminishes the same force in terms of political utility.

The digital and cultural surveillance system through Google, Facebook, Instagram, Swiggy, Zomato and others are all the tools of surveillance for data aggregation, which according to Foucault is governing through freedom where the people are self directed. This new market economy works on the unquestioned logic of accumulation in which surveillance is a foundational mechanism in the transformation of investment into profit. The Instagram algorithm for accessing location, Mobile Apps and Governmental sites to access the location of the user is mandatory to gain the access of the feature of the app or site. The case of meta 'Eavesdropping' shows how period apps have become a data goldmine. The tech giant was found to have illegally collected user information. The millions of people who use the Flo app are asked to provide personal information along with intimate details about their sexual health, menstrual cycles and gynaecologist health through a series of questions. Until 2021, Meta automatically received information from each survey question and used the data for advertising and The Cambridge Analytica scandal involving Facebook data has turned technology companies into reluctant political players in global diplomatic crises.

These all have led to a growing "Security dilemma" and "data nationalism", where countries increasingly demand data localization where they store data on physical servers within national borders to prevent foreign agencies foreign. But it also makes that data more vulnerable to the host country's own intelligence agencies and increases the costs of data protection for the companies involved.

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“Surveillance as Cultural Practice” by Torin Monaghan advocates on how surveillance studies have evolved from a focus on institutional level power dynamics like Panopticon towards “social studies of surveillance”. This new approach can be proactively repurposed by groups operating outside government or corporate structures to achieve collective empowerment. One of the instruments among many can be the use of RTI Act 2005 in the Indian legal context to increase the transparency and accountability of the government from the citizens. The RTI Act is the clear example inversion of panopticon on the government from the citizens. It empowers the citizens to look at the newer approach in the ‘Age of Surveillance’, for self protection and empowerment, to deconstruct entrenched social structures and institutions for assurances of justice for vulnerable groups.

Foucault as a deconstructionist and critical theorist through Panopticon and Surveillance works to grasp the social reality for normativity and transformation aiming to change both our knowledge of our world and to understand the structures of our world more deeply and rationally.

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PROMISE OF THE ALGORITHMIC CERBERUS: DANGERS OF PREDICTIVE POLICING

WRITTEN BY: AFREEN

Philip K. Dick's *Minority Report* is a 1956 sci-fi novella about the 'Precrime' system, which supposedly arrested criminals before they committed murders. Similar themes of extreme surveillance and policing are explored in shows like *Psycho-Pass*, *Bodies*, etc. The popularised concept of an Orwellian Thought Police also explores a similar concept of a surveillance system with extraordinary powers over its citizens which undermines their individual autonomy and gives into the risk of totalitarianism.

The rise of Artificial Intelligence and its perception as a collaborative tool for security has now started paving roads, which if not scrutinised, may lead to similar futures.

● How Predictive Policing Works

It uses Machine-Learning algorithms to forecast criminal activity, with historical crime data based on social media content, CCTV footage, biometrics, socio-economic metrics and weather patterns even becoming the inputs. This can be done through two methods: Location-based (hotspots/timeframes where crimes are likely to occur) and Person-based (individual identification based on arrest histories and behaviouralism).

• Promises and Steps taken

AI is advocated to overcome human biases and human methods by optimizing resource allocation. Departments claim that they can make operations safer and cheaper by preventing harm before it happens.

McKinsey Global Institute says that integrating AI would reduce urban crime by 30-40% and emergency response times by one-third, while Marinus Analytics suggests that by utilizing AI and geospatial analysis to monitor missing persons in sex trafficking, US organizations have seen much success. Firm Ironside in Manchester asserts that their predictive model reduced the effects of crime by 28% in just five weeks.

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Countries like Japan and Brazil have also stepped into the arena, with Japan adopting 'Crime Nabi', increasing efficiency by 50%, and the system's subsequent export to Brazil stopped the theft of metal cables in Belo Horizonte.

Maharashtra, India saw the integration of the MARVEL system in 2014, sharing police data with AI firms to autogenerate case files.

- Limitations

The concept of Security in itself is flawed and has been criticised by various schools. The State being the sole wielder of force, and earning legitimacy implies that its agents (i.e. the army, the police, etc.) are the state-sanctioned force-wielders. This also means that any of the State's biases and historical perceptions of certain communities, ethnicities and groups may colour the fact that which type of groups become targets of such type of policing. Crime does not occur in a vacuum, but is rather the product of various social, political, economic and psychological factors, along with environments.

Factors like historic injustices, deprivation of resources which lead to such crimes may get ignored by machines, i.e. Human biases may lead to biases developing in these algorithms which may lead to wrongful actions carried out in the name of security.

Arbitrary arrests and infringement on personal liberties can discourage free assembly and may lead to erosion of limits on the State.

- Is it already happening?

Examples around the world may show that this process is already being initiated.

UAE saw a Dubai police conference, in which "sentiment analysis software" (inferring mood from facial expressions) was marketed alongside hacking tools. Another system is Dubai's "brain fingerprint" system, which reportedly generates insights into a suspect's memory when shown crime scene stimulus images.

China's Xinjiang province has Integrated Joint Operations Platform (IJOP), which monitors everything from electricity usage to even religious habits (which is concerning when we remember that we're talking about China). It flags "pre-criminal" behavior, allowing authorities to detain individuals who have not yet committed a crime. This model is now another export in the Chinese "Digital Silk Road."

Democratic nations are not immune to these abuses either.

LAPD and Dataminr: Internal records indicated that between 2023 and 2024, the LAPD was notified about more than 50 protests about the war in Gaza, which prompted concern about the monitoring of political dissent.

VioGén System in Spain: This system was created to prevent domestic violence by focusing on recidivism. It came under heavy scrutiny when a woman was killed just weeks after reporting her partner. She was considered a "medium risk" by the system. This is what can come out of excessive reliance on algorithmic "safety" scores.

Nanotechnology and Spyware are being used by large 'police tech' entities and Google's PaliGemma makes it easier for AI to analyze surveillance data through its upgraded visual-language model.

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The EU has introduced regulations for this through its Article 5, passed in 2025, which prohibits the use of AI to predict the probability of a crime occurring. However, there are exceptions for terrorism, murder, and human trafficking, which may lead to some complications. However, this alone is not enough.

The Citizen Lab Recommendations:

A report from the University of Toronto suggests rigid safeguards, including:

- Mandatory consultations with marginalized communities before deployment.
- Judicial oversight (judges must sign off on system use).
- Maximum transparency regarding training data and regular third-party audits.
- The right for individuals to verify and correct their personal data in police databases.

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SURVEILLING OURSELVES INTO SELF-COMMODIFICATION

WRITTEN BY: ROHA SIDHU

In the digitised world, our fingerprints and our eyes biometrics have been recorded somewhere in the 'big data'. We are continually pushing ourselves to think psychologically of ourselves as both the subject and the object of surveillance. Through the panopticon, which Foucault discusses in his work, *Discipline and Punish* (1977), the foundational knowledge of power and surveillance unfolds to us. His analysis of the panopticon as a device of surveillance leads to an understanding of the discipline the gaze imposes on people, and it fundamentally changes how one behaves.

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He traces the departure from brutal physical punishments to prison, the panopticon. With the introduction of prison, the content of punishment changed along with it. The introduction of the panopticon had an impact on the functioning of the social order.

● **FOUCAULT AND INTERNAL MONITORING**

In the panopticon, the guard can see the incarcerated, but because of the way the panopticon was designed by Bentham, the prisoners could not see the guard.

This, for Foucault (1977), leads to the internalisation of being monitored continuously. This is because one is always aware of one's visibility to the panopticon. The power that acts on people is not only omnipresent but also flows in the microcosms of life. It remains the manifestation in our social anxieties of being watched. Through this, one can understand the way the panopticon allows a few people to surveil the many. The disciplinary society in which Foucault's work is situated is different from ours. The society's obsession with technology has grown, and surveillance has changed its forms.

While the panopticon was the surveillance of a few over many, Thomas Mathiesen, in his article *The Viewer Society* (1997), posits a further development. He postulates the notion of "synopticon." Here, according to Mathiesen, "Concurring in detail with its historical development, we have seen the development of a unique and enormously extensive system enabling the many to see and contemplate the few"

For him, the explosion of mass media, where the many have been able to see the few, has also become part of society. It is not only a panopticon that structures society; another reciprocal phenomenon has occurred: the synopticon. Hence, we are living in a viewer society.

Power continues to permeate society. The media and its information continue to shape us in the way that the actors in the media have the power to highlight some agendas while hiding others. A perception of importance is manufactured by the media figures we see. The media becomes the controller of our consciousness, as per Mathiesen (1997). Similarly, power continually changes its form as it permeates society. Byung Chul-Han, in his work, *Psychopolitics: Neoliberalism and New Technologies of Power* (2017), demonstrates the increasingly psychological stronghold that the technologies have over people's minds. The disciplinary power has changed into friendliness. The power lies in the 'permissivity' that imbues the technologies.

Power is positioning itself as liberation while shedding its negative connotations. Han (2017) calls it smart power. For him, instead of coercion, it directly plays with the psyche of people. Free selection (Auswahl) replaces free choice (Wahl). Free choice is eliminated.

The smart power is friendly; it comes in the form of Likes. A person will talk about their lives openly for the likes, where technology is designed in a way that people participate by confiding their preferences, opinions and wishes. The neo-liberal economy works on the principle of like, a mechanism of removing oneself from the self. People turn outwards for their decisions, their opinions, their preferences, in their pursuit of the like. Power is friendly, as there is little resistance when one pushes for self-optimisation. The body was the place where much of the disciplinary action took place, but in the neo-liberal economy, as per Han (2017), the action is on the soul.

As the market and surveillance state continue to merge, the people become the commodity to be exploited. With the continued intermingling of the digitalscape, the intrusion into our lives and our information has increased. Social media companies play an important role in extracting and collecting our data. Our personal data is currency to the multinational corporations. The data acts as a collective psychogram for the companies. Big Data is then used for predicting as well as generating our behaviour. We are constantly pushed into our echochambers, where our views are moulded according to what the algorithms in place have predicted. We constantly view the few people, while materialising ourselves according to the friendliness that the neoliberal economy imposes on us.

The continued indictment of ourselves in the cyber spaces, we not only have virtual personalities, but they have started to impact the way we proceed in our everyday lives. The self starts to see itself as a commodity; we are constantly instrumentalising ourselves to an end. The smart power homogenises certain interests through promoting commercials or adverts according to the information that is stored with them. Our data is not only stored but also continuously analysed. We become data to be rendered and are denied our humanity in the process.

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Through this, our psyche is shaping itself to see the self through the lens of a commodity that needs to be sold in the market, a hobby becomes a commodity, our leisure becomes a skill to be marketed, our bodies, our minds, all fall into the trap of smart power that holds our hands into selection from what is available, and what will sell.

This pushes people into compartmentalising themselves, into boxes that could be used and disposed of accordingly. The algorithms of media not only push masses into echo chambers but also exclude people who do not have the same economic viability in the system. Similar to how commodities work, some are seen as useful, while others are regarded as waste. The digitalscape built on algorithms continues to commodify the users and dehumanise a swath of humanity.

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CONTAINMENT, CONTROL AND SURVEILLANCE: A QUALITATIVE INQUIRY INTO EATING DISORDERS AND THE COVID-19 PANDEMIC

WRITTEN BY: DIKSHA SINGH

The COVID-19 pandemic and the subsequent national lockdowns in the United Kingdom created a specific set of geographical and social circumstances that significantly changed the experiences that people with eating disorders lived. The research article titled **containment, control and Surveillance**, Ellys Feather, the author, analyses how containment and loss of both the public and personal boundaries led to the heightened experience of being observed both extrinsically and intrusively. Through the application of qualitative interviews and autoethnographic data, the study outlines a social geography of eating disorders by going beyond oversimplified biomedical conceptions to challenge how the pandemic rearranged the home, as a place of increased surveillance and psychological negotiation.

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● DIFFERENT LEVELS

The core of this question is the notion of surveillance working at different levels during the lockdown. On the macro-governmental level, the whole population was forced into the strict regime of containment, with the outdoors being restricted to one hour in a day. This imposed isolation was a reflection of the self-imposed limitations often encountered by eating disorder sufferers, creating a union between government regulations and the pathological dictums of the disorder. But the greatest change was done at the micro-domestic level. With the indulgence of the offices, gyms, and restaurants, the home took in the roles of all other areas of life. This physical breakdown masked the previous differentiated action of the third-space which was either public or private under constant observation of family, or spouses or roommates.

The paper describes the house in the era as being a panopticon, a term borrowed by Michel Foucault to refer to a model where one thinks he is constantly watched, whether he is under supervision or not at any particular time. This was equivalent to making the kitchen, which was previously a bingeing or restriction arena, a stage to the participants of the study.

Their presence served as a disciplinary power, in which the appearance of one of the family members into the room could cause panic or need to do normalcy.

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Surveillance was not always aimed at being ugly in most instances it was a manifestation by a loved one that someone cared. However, the increased signal often ushered in resistance as opposed to recovery since the participants claimed to develop elaborate measures to avoid the household gaze, e.g. hiding food, enjoying exercise under the cover of darkness or making the bathroom the only truly individualized place of disordered behavior.

On top of the physical presence of others, the pandemic changed the age of digital surveillance. The process of society switching to remote work and using video conferencing platforms to interact has compelled individuals to spend the entire day staring at themselves too long. Feather demonstrates that this virtual gaze enabled a process which is referred to as body-checking. The screen, as a digital mirror on such a platform as Zoom, amplifies self-observation and enhances the mind/body dichotomy. Social Media exacerbated this issue.

One of the most relevant conclusions made in the paper is the concept of guising, which is a type of self-psychological surveying. The author notes that the new normal of the pandemic allowed most people to disguise their disordered behavior. Over training was often repackaged as a way of staying active or staying heart healthy thus justifying it to themselves and to others. Since most people suddenly donned their masks due to the pandemic, which promoted health-positive changes like home cooking and walking every day, the symptoms of eating disorder could be hidden behind the facade of productivity or even wellness. This inner policing enabled the disorder to thrive under the pretext of socially desirable pandemic activities to develop an envelope of falsification and make detection and treatment difficult.

On the contrary, the paper also concerns the risks of under-surveillance of people living alone. On these occasions, the confinement of the flat or house turned into a vacuum where eating disorders behaviors could act freely. The studies indicate that the two extremes of observation and lack of observation are highly hazardous to mental well-being and recovery. Surveillance was not present and this allowed the development of subtle behaviors that could easily go unnoticed until they became firmly internalized.

Another major theme is the temporal aspect of surveillance. The paper outlines how the absence of external rhythms in the form of commuting or attending work created the hard, self-disciplined schedules. Such habits were used as a system to regain authority in a very unstable world, but these routines turned out to be a kind of internal jail. The expectation of food or even the mental strain of establishing how to pass on food during the occasional social events was mentally tiring. The results indicate that these habits were not simply automatic, but rather non-habitual in a way in which simply maintaining the practice required exhausting mental effort on an ongoing basis.

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To conclude, the study by Ellys Feather indicates that the COVID-19 pandemic did not only pose health crisis but was also a spatial and psychological one to people affected by eating disorders. The surveillance geographies that were built throughout the lock-down, such as watchful eyes of family or digital eyes of webcams, formed a complex network of power and resistance.

The recording of these experiential realities in the study is that recovery is a non-linear experience that is heavily affected by the spaces that physical beings occupy. The way surveillance works in the domestic realm is critical to building more understanding and helpful approaches to support those who must struggle with the challenges of eating disorders in a world that has already embraced the post-pandemic reality.

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FACING UP TO THE RISKS OF AUTOMATED FACIAL RECOGNITION TECHNOLOGIES IN INDIAN LAW ENFORCEMENT

WRITTEN BY: SOUMADRI MUKHERJEE

The law enforcement forces have now deployed Automated Facial Recognition Technology, as a high speed biometric search engine. Ameena Jauhar in her article, titled, "Facing up to the risks of Automated Facial Recognition in Indian Law Enforcement." While expressing three major apprehensions towards AFTR, claims that though this technology allows mass screenings of individuals, is yet only efficient in theory and is plagued by inaccuracies in reality. As a result technology remains prone to misuse, often owing to biasedness, opacity and discrimination.

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Jauhar cites the inaccuracies of AFRT deployed in the USA and notes down a higher error rate in case of the Afro-American Diaspora and Women. The biggest contention with its deployment is its high rate of inaccuracy.

● **AUTOMATION BIAS**

The dogmatism of the 'automation bias', a blind belief in the decision making ability of the algorithmic system, seems to be the validated cause. In the absence of the legal protection of the citizens' data, AFRT is a dangerous technology, poised to turn itself into a theocratic state, curbing several civil rights. The unregulated deployment of AFRT violates the due process of law established under Article 21. It operates behind an opaque wall, under the guise of maintaining national integrity, makes itself impenetrable, even to the Fundamental Right of 'Right to Information'. The data is left to the absolute discretion of the law enforcement in India, generating a main catalyst of a foreboding, looming calamity, at the plausible misuse of the public data.

Jauhar commends EU's and its attempts to ensure an ethically compliant AFRT and protect the rights of its citizens. Further the entire law making process surrounding AFRT has been subject to much debate and discussions along with different stakeholders. This not only instills a sense of trust in the public eye for its government and its service, but is also democratic in nature.

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According to the Jauhar, the EU aims to reap the benefits of AFRT while ensuring a minimisation of all viable risks. They now claim that India's facial diversity poses a major risk to the deployment of AFRT, fearing a plausible abuse of the data by the state. The absence of any law establishing the procedure or situations where AFRT can be used for monitoring and collecting data increases the stakes. In the absence of such laws courts are forced to strike a clear boundary between individual privacy and civil rights.

In India the citizens are contorted into living in a 'Black Box Society'. Questions regarding who, how and when these laws are made, were brought to inception. Finally, Jauhar states that there is an urgent need for a robust legal system to define and limit the use of AFRT. There should be stakeholder engagement to better understand the legal, constitutional and regulatory issues associated with it .

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REVISITING FOUCAULT'S PANOPTICON: HOW DOES AI SURVEILLANCE TRANSFORM EDUCATIONAL NORMS?

WRITTEN BY: SAANVI RANDHAWA

This is a research article published in 2025 in the 46th volume of British Journal Of Sociology Of Education written by Ruixun Dai, Matthew Krehl Edward Thomas and Shaun Rawolle who are all based at the School Of Education, Deakin University in Australia. The main purpose of this research article is to analyse shifting power dynamics in highly technology driven education especially in the context of Artificial Intelligence. This research is based on the qualitative responses from 27 stakeholders with no geographical restrictions including students, teachers, administrators and parents.

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The article states that machine learning is not neutral but an active agent of algorithmic control, reflecting a post-panoptic power structure. AI-powered surveillance systems such as smart cameras, cloud-based educational platforms, and software tracking students' online activities, are rapidly evolving within schools, often collecting large amounts of data on students and storing it indefinitely.

● SURVEILLANCE CAPITALISM

This surveillance capitalism is led by market driven imperative where students' and teachers' personal data are continuously collected, commodified, and utilised by major technology companies under the mask of educational innovation. AI-surveillance in education has become a widespread phenomenon driven by the global ed-tech markets which has unfortunately reshaped pedagogical principles. This post-panoptic power structure is subtly altering the behaviours of students and teachers.

Here, the stakeholders are not only influenced by the awareness of being watched but also by predictive feedback and algorithmic norms.

Foucault demonstrates how surveillance systems operate in schools, where both teachers and students are constantly monitored. Teachers behave as the director in the panoptic system, overseeing students' activities, correcting mistakes, and maintaining discipline. Similarly, students internalise this surveillance and adjust their behaviours accordingly. Another interesting phenomenon is normalisation which happens as individuals unconsciously become aware of being constantly observed such as school attendance tracking systems may lead students to conform to classroom conduct codes and arrive on time.

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Through various technologies, surveillance has become more widespread and harder to notice such as the widespread and extensive use of CCTV cameras in school campuses, biometric facial recognition systems being utilised in China and Australia to track student attendance, body cameras being worn by teachers in the United Kingdom, online learning platforms, and AI-powered monitoring systems analysing students' browsing behaviours and even emotional responses in US and Australia. The boundary between the surveiller and the surveilled has blurred and stakeholders are resisting these technologies as well. The substantial amounts of data generated from algorithms influence educational norms and reshape interactions based on predictive feedback rather than human discretion. AI-era surveillance technologies have become increasingly interconnected, forming an inescapable network. AI-driven surveillance in education has moved beyond simple monitoring to systems that collect, analyse, predict, and shape behaviour through data and automated feedback.

Using tools such as facial-recognition cameras and online activity tracking, schools increasingly rely on algorithmic decision-making that subtly influences teachers' methods and students' engagement. This creates a post-panoptic environment where surveillance is internalised and guided by AI norms rather than visible control. However, these systems operate with limited transparency and reinforce power imbalances, often marginalising less digitally literate or sociology-economically disadvantaged groups. While improving efficiency and safety, AI surveillance raises serious concerns about privacy, agency, trust, inequality, and the growing transfer of educational authority from humans to algorithms.

This study investigated how AI-powered systems are experienced as surveillance in education and how they reshape power relations by conducting a qualitative, anonymous online survey with key stakeholders—students, teachers, administrators, and parents. Participants were recruited through social media platforms such as Facebook, LinkedIn, WeChat, and RED, and were required to be over 18 and to have direct experience with AI in educational contexts. Focusing on Chinese- and English-speaking respondents ensured that their views could be accurately interpreted while also allowing for a geographically diverse sample. In total, 27 participants aged 22–60 (9 students, 4 teachers, 4 administrators, and 10 parents) took part, with the sample size determined by theoretical saturation. The survey used open-ended questions to generate detailed personal accounts, which were examined through thematic analysis. Rather than concentrating on a specific educational level or demographic differences, the study identified broader patterns in how AI surveillance is perceived, how it influences behavior and decision-making, and what stakeholders gradually come to accept as normal. Although experiences varied—teachers noted increased efficiency, administrators highlighted automated tasks, and parents valued personalized learning—participants consistently expressed concerns about privacy. A central finding was that many stakeholders are willing to trade a degree of autonomy for the convenience and functionality AI systems provide.

By bringing together these diverse perspectives, the study offers a comprehensive view of how AI surveillance is becoming normalised and how it is quietly reshaping educational practices, authority, and everyday interactions.

The data were analysed using a flexible thematic analysis to identify recurring patterns and deeper meanings in participants' narratives. Following Braun and Clarke's six-step process and using NVivo, responses were translated, transcribed, repeatedly reviewed, and coded in relation to the research questions and Foucault's concepts of surveillance, disciplinary power, and normalisation. Initial codes examined what aspects of life participants felt were monitored, how AI surveillance reshaped their behaviours and perceptions, and what new norms emerged. Similar codes were then grouped into broader themes, refined through researcher consensus to ensure credibility. The analysis prioritised overarching patterns across stakeholders, with themes presented according to their frequency and prominence in the data.

The thematic analysis of the 27 survey responses produced four overarching themes that explain how AI-powered surveillance is reshaping education: the normalisation of ubiquitous surveillance and behavioural control, the prioritisation of efficiency over autonomy, the reaffirmation of the human element in AI-assisted education, and the need for human-AI collaboration. Together, these findings show that AI, big data, and IoT technologies have made monitoring continuous and inescapable across both educational and everyday digital environments. Although participants were aware of constant data collection through platforms, smartphones, and automated systems, many regarded it as inevitable and adjusted their behaviour accordingly, reflecting a post-panoptic form of self-regulation in line with AI-driven norms.

At the same time, respondents across all stakeholder groups valued the efficiency AI brings to teaching, administration, and learning. Automated feedback, translation, assessment, and personalised learning reduced workload and improved performance, leading many to accept reduced autonomy, limited transparency, and privacy risks. Despite recognising the "black box" nature of algorithms and the possibility of declining critical thinking or independent inquiry, most prioritised speed, convenience, and data-driven decision-making, indicating a shift in what is considered valuable in education.

However, participants consistently stressed that AI cannot replace the emotional, ethical, and relational dimensions of education. Mentoring, value formation, creativity, and social development were seen as fundamentally human processes that require empathy and contextual understanding. This has produced a new normalisation in which AI is viewed as a powerful support tool but not as a substitute for educators.

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Concerns about bias in algorithms, unreliable outputs, and weak regulation further reinforced the view that human oversight is essential. Respondents emphasised that AI should function as an advisory system, with humans retaining decision-making authority and establishing evolving regulatory frameworks. Overall, the findings suggest that while AI surveillance is transforming power relations and everyday practices in education, stakeholders are moving toward a model of cautious, collaborative coexistence in which human agency remains central.

Using a Foucauldian lens, this study shows that AI surveillance in education has moved from passive monitoring to actively shaping behaviour, norms, and power through data-driven control. While stakeholders prioritise efficiency, they still value human judgement and emotional engagement. The findings call for ethical policies that ensure equity, transparency, and the preservation of human agency.

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BLACK BOX SOCIETY

WRITTEN BY: ZAINAB NAZKI

In the 21st century, how does power work? Who has it? Why do they specifically have it? And what did they do to get it? The *Black Box Society: The Secret Algorithms that Control Money and Information* (2015) by Frank Pasquale examines just this. It examines how powerful corporations use secret algorithms to control critical aspects of modern life. These include finance, search engines, credit scoring, employment screening, insurance, and online reputations, all this without transparency or accountability.

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Some might call it the “Unknown Unknowns,” “Black Swans,” and “Deep Secrets,” for a lack of transparency. These gaps in knowledge have powerful consequences, and these gaps are maintained deliberately. This lack of knowledge is profitable for the elite to escape regulations. Our knowledge about these companies and governments is constrained by the laws of trade secrecy and the laws of privacy. The biggest question asked by the authors is, “To whose benefit are these laws made and followed?”

● WHO BENEFITS FROM SURVEILLANCE?

They point out the fact that these big companies hoard large amounts of customer data with little regulation, so the privacy of data laws largely applies to these companies and the elites, and not the common people. We are surveilled online at all times, and our data is recorded piece by piece. “Anonymizing software may shield us for a little while, but who knows whether trying to hide isn’t itself the ultimate red flag for watchful authorities?” Surveillance cameras, data brokers, sensor networks, and “super-cookies” record how fast we drive, what pills we take, what books we read, and what websites we visit.

Big Pharma companies can hide the dangers of new drugs behind the garb of trade secrecy, and the banks hide behind shell corporations to obscure tax liabilities. The power of secrecy points towards the power of knowledge. And to scrutinize others while avoiding scrutiny yourself is one of the most important forms of power. Internet companies collect more and more data on their customers, but fight the regulations that would let the same users exercise some control over the resulting large collections of data. On the other hand, these companies probably have data on very intimate details of our lives, and this is used to influence our decisions in every aspect of our lives through curated algorithms.

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Financial institutions use complex algorithms that determine loan eligibility, set insurance premiums, and predict consumer behaviour. Yet consumers cannot see how these scores are contested.

Big data looms in the areas of reputation, search engines, and finance. However, to completely dissect this is very difficult, the black box of big data. Hidden algorithms combined with massive data collection and corporate secrecy provide the big companies with unchecked power. Pasquale argues that we live in a “black box society,” where decision-making systems are opaque: we cannot see how they work, challenge their outcomes, or understand why certain decisions are made about us. “We are entering an era where invisible computational systems determine life chances, without public knowledge or democratic control.”

Pasquale also explores how platforms like Google and Facebook use proprietary algorithms to rank search results and curate news feeds. This gives them a monopoly over shaping public opinion. This is capable of influencing political, economic, and social power. Reputation systems can easily damage an individual's social standing. Data brokers create “Digital Dossiers” without consent. Algorithms tend to reinforce inequality and discrimination and reproduce structural biases. Even if these systems seem neutral, the data and incentives behind them are not. Since these systems are considered trade secrets, they are protected from public view. Search engines act as regulators of visibility without democratic accountability.

About the financial systems, Pasquale explains how financial institutions increasingly rely on automated scoring systems to evaluate individuals. Credit scores, risk models, and predictive analytics shape access to housing, jobs, and loans. Consumers are constantly monitored and categorized, and in all of this, errors are common, yet the correction mechanisms are weak. Moreover, these processes have become too complex for meaningful public oversight. Pasquale also speaks about the 2008 financial crisis, which is framed as both a failure of transparency and accountability.

At the end, Pasquale proposes reforms such as stronger protection laws, algorithmic transparency requirements, regulatory oversight, and professional ethics in tech industries. He advocates for an auditable accountability framework. He reiterates that democracy requires transparency and institutional oversight. According to him, if algorithmic systems remain unregulated, economic and informational power will concentrate further in private hands.

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